

This document forms section three of the University of Bath's Responsible Research Assessment Guidance and should be read alongside [the full guidance](#). You can find more information on the [RRA webpage](#).

5. Evidencing quality – what metrics can tell us and how to use them responsibly

Key points covered in this section:

- Use metrics and indicators responsibly, selecting the best available evidence and contextualising it appropriately.
- Avoid metrics that misrepresent quality.
- Use the tables to find out what evidence could support the assessment of each of the three facets of quality (contribution, quality of content, and influence/impact/visibility/reach).

As set out in our institutional [principles](#), responsible research assessment ensures quantitative indicators and metrics are chosen for their robustness and reliability. No indicator or metric is perfect so we must use the best available evidence and ensure that it is appropriately contextualised.

Both assessors and those being assessed need a common understanding of what metrics indicate, their limitations and which metrics or types of evidence are, and are not, considered valid for assessment at the University of Bath (as approved by Research and Knowledge Exchange Committee in September 2025, and Academic Staff Committee in November, 2025). This helps ensure that:

- individuals being assessed are informed on what is considered the 'best possible evidence' and so can make their case as effectively as possible.
- individuals can effectively identify the outputs that they would like to put forward for assessment (for example, if an assessment process requires them to nominate their top three outputs).
- assessors are not provided with evidence or metrics, listed as 'avoid', that they cannot consider, but can then be difficult to disregard.

There are metrics and indicators that should be avoided in research assessment (see Table 2), either because they are not reliable indicators and/or because better evidence options exist.

Table 3: Metrics to avoid (approved by RKEC and ASC)

Metrics to avoid	Limitations
Journal impact factor	Describes average reach and/or visibility of outputs within the journal, but not the reach and/or visibility of the specific output, the quality of the output, or its impact. The content of the output is much more important than the publication venue.
Journal-level citation metrics that are field-weighted e.g. SNIP, SJR, Article influence score.	Describes average reach and/or visibility of outputs within the journal, normalised by field, but not the reach and/or visibility of the specific output, the quality of the output, or its impact. The quality of the output is more important than the publication venue.
Output count	<p>Used in assessment, output counts can drive undesired behaviours (e.g., to publish larger quantities of lower quality work rather than smaller quantities of higher quality work).</p> <p>Output counts bias towards individuals with longer careers and traditional academic career paths. Output counts disadvantage individuals who have spent time in industry, taken time away from work for caring responsibilities or illness, part-time colleagues, and those earlier in their careers. Does not account for differences in publication norms between disciplines.</p>
H-index	Biased towards individuals with longer careers/ traditional academic career paths. Disadvantages individuals who have spent time in industry, taken time away from work for caring responsibilities or illness, part-time colleagues, and those earlier in their careers. Largely accumulates over time, creating age-related bias.
Author-level citation metrics	Largely accumulates over time, creating age-related bias.
Raw citation counts	Decontextualised citation data that is not field-weighted or by year will not give a meaningful picture of the reach of the output relative to others in similar fields/ years of publication. Citations may also be positive or negative, and do not always imply positive impact/ visibility in a field.
Ranking or reputation of affiliated organisation	The identity of an institution cannot reliably indicate the quality of all researchers within it. Many low-ranking universities have exceptional departments/ research teams within them, and vice versa. In addition, exceptional researchers make judgements on which institution to join based on a variety of factors, including family circumstances. As such, in line with approved CoARA commitments, we do not allow 'trickle down' of institutional status to researcher assessments.

The following three tables (see below) describe types of evidence that may be utilised to support assessments of each of the three facets of quality (contribution, quality of content, and influence/impact/visibility/reach).

This list is not exhaustive. Metrics and evidence should only be used for the specific facet of quality that the table describes.

A common example of metrics being used inappropriately is where a metric indicating visibility, impact, influence, or reach is used as a proxy for the quality of an output's content. This practice should be avoided.

Although these metrics and evidence types have their limitations, they represent examples of 'best available evidence' and have been approved by RKEC and ASC.

The tables categorise each evidence type as:

- **Central evidence:** This is in line with the first of our six core principles that states "research assessment [...] is based on expert judgement for which qualitative evaluation and peer review is central." Where the assessment requires an individual to submit a statement (for example, a cover letter or description of research contribution in a promotions case) as a central part of the process, this should always be supported by evidence. Where peer review is a central form of assessment, assessors may still wish to use other supporting evidence to challenge or support their assessments.
- **Supporting evidence:** Examples are provided of quantitative and qualitative information that might be considered in an assessment process to evidence claims or assessments of quality. The list is not exhaustive, and individuals may submit alternative evidence (except for items listed under 'avoid' in Table 2).

Contribution

Table 4: examples of types of evidence for 'contribution'

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Central	Contextualised evidence statement of the individual's contribution.	The role that this person played in the construction of the research output.	<p>For multi-author outputs, an individual's description of their contribution may not reflect the understanding of, or be 'agreed' by, all authors.</p> <p>Consider that contextualised evidence statements may disadvantage individuals who are not native speakers of English, who come from international academic contexts, or who are neurodivergent.</p>
Supporting	Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) statement https://credit.niso.org/	The role that this individual played in the construction of the output, but not necessarily the relative significance of contribution.	CRediT has its origins in Life Sciences and may not capture all roles played across different disciplines. For multi-author outputs, the CRediT statement may not be 'agreed' by all authors.
Supporting	Authorship position	The significance of the individual's contribution relative to other authors, but not an absolute reflection of the significance, nor the nature of the contribution.	The order in which authors are listed is different across disciplines. In some cases, lists are alphabetic, meaning they are meaningless for assessments of contribution.
Supporting	Percentage contribution	The individuals' self-reported perception of the significance of their contribution relative to other authors, but not an absolute reflection of the significance, nor the nature of the contribution.	This is a self-reported quantification of a contribution which might be more reliably described qualitatively. An individual's perception of their percentage contribution may not be 'agreed' by all authors. Where all authors are asked to estimate their percentage contribution, there is no mechanism to stop the total contributions exceeding 100%, meaning estimates may be unreliable.

Quality of content

Table 5: examples of types of evidence for 'quality of content'

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Central	Contextualised evidence statement of the quality of the output's content. <i>This may consider the novelty, significance, and rigour as well as research design, integrity and ethics.</i>	An indication of the output's quality according to the individual.	Consider that contextualised evidence statements may disadvantage individuals who are not native speakers of English, who come from international academic contexts, or who are neurodivergent.
Central	Provision of the output itself	An indication of the output's quality according to the individual assessor(s)	Consider that peer review can be subject to bias. Assessors should be sufficiently close to the discipline to deploy their expert judgement on the novelty, significance, and rigour of the output, to include appropriateness of research design, evidence of ethical conduct etc. Having a panel of assessors would help ensure any disciplinary bias or knowledge gaps are minimised in the assessment process.

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Supporting	Internal peer review scores	A quantitative indication of the quality of the output as assessed by expert peers in an internal review process.	<p>Consider that peer review can be subject to bias.</p> <p>Internal peer review can be subject to particular biases as colleagues are reviewing each other's work. Different practices across faculties, School and departments, means that not all individuals will have access to scores from internal peer review processes.</p>
Supporting	Internal peer review comments	A qualitative indication of the quality of the output as assessed by expert peers in an internal review process.	<p>Consider that peer review can be subject to bias.</p> <p>Internal peer review can be subject to particular biases as colleagues are reviewing each other's work. Different practices across faculties, School and departments, means that not all individuals will have comments or feedback on their work from internal peer review processes.</p>
Supporting	External peer review comments	A qualitative indication of the quality of the output as assessed by expert peers in an external review process.	<p>Consider that peer review can be subject to bias.</p>
Supporting	Other reviews (e.g. book, event or exhibition review)	A qualitative indication of the quality of the output as assessed by reviewer(s).	<p>It may be helpful to consider the expertise of the reviewer, where this is not part of a formal peer review process.</p>
Supporting	Prizes and awards	The output has received recognition.	<p>It may be helpful to consider who has made the award and on what basis i.e. what were the assessment criteria?</p> <p>Consider the frequency and value of the prize/award.</p>

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Supporting	Rigour of a publisher's peer review process	The peer review process that an output has been through in order to be published.	Consider the peer review process from commissioning to completion, including the nature and number of reviewers, editorial oversight, and other evidence of rigour. The purpose of peer review in this context is to evaluate the output's quality and its suitability for publication in a particular outlet. There may be reasons that an output is deemed as high quality but not suitable for publication in a particular outlet.

Impact, influence, visibility, and reach

Table 6: examples of types of evidence for 'impact, influence, visibility, and reach'

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Central	Contextualised evidence statement of the reach, visibility, impact and/or influence of the output	The impact or influence that the output has had according to the individual.	Consider that contextualised evidence statements may disadvantage individuals who are not native speakers of English, who come from international academic contexts, or who are neurodivergent.
Supporting	Policy citations	The number of times a research output has been cited, and in which policy documents.	Consider the nature of the citations. Research may influence policy and decision making in indirect ways that are not always trackable via policy citations. Citations can be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'.
Supporting	Number of patents	Whether the research output has led to a commercial patent, or the patent has been cited in research.	It is possible to file a patent that is not used. Consider the impact of the patents.
Supporting	Field weighted/ normalised citations by year of publication such as FWCI	How the reach and/or visibility of the output measures in relation to the average reach and/or visibility for similar publications, but not the quality of its content, or the nature of citations (+ve/-ve), or its impact.	Field weighted citation metrics are only of use in fields where there are enough outputs and citations to provide a robust baseline metric. Citations can be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'. Citation metrics may not be an accurate indicator of reach for all fields, disciplines or output types. For some researchers, significant publications will not be on the most commonly used databases.

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Supporting	Citation metrics that are based on the use of percentiles (within the field) rather than averages	How the reach and/or visibility of the output measures in relation to the average reach and/or visibility for similar publications, but not the quality of its content, or the nature of citations (+ve/-ve), or its impact.	Citations can be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'. Citation metrics may not be an accurate indicator of reach for all fields, disciplines or output types. For some researchers, significant publications will not be on the most commonly used databases.
Supporting	Collaboration citation metrics (e.g. international co-authorship, national co-authorship, academic / corporate co-authorship)	Whether the individual has published with international/ national/ corporate peers, but not the quality of the output or its impact.	Data may not always be complete (dependent upon good affiliation practice by authors). International, national or corporate collaboration may be more or less appropriate depending on the nature and aims of the research. As with outputs counts, counting international collaborations risks focussing on volume rather than quality, and may drive undesired behaviours.
Supporting	Event / conference attendees	The reach and/or visibility of the output, but not the quality of its content, its impact, or its reception.	Attendance to events or conference papers could be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'. Expected attendance can vary significantly according to discipline, field and language.

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Supporting	Repository views for open access outputs	The number of views an output has had but not the quality of its content, its impact, or its reception.	Views are not an accurate measure of consumption or how many people have read the output. Views could be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'. Expected number of views can vary significantly according to discipline, field and language. Views may be split across more than one platform if the item has been deposited more than once. Not all platforms record views and downloads to the same standards, so metrics may not be comparable unless using the COUNTER standard.
Supporting	Downloads for open access outputs	The number of times an output has been downloaded but not the quality of its content, its impact, or its reception.	Downloads is not an accurate measure of consumption or how many people have read the output. Downloads could be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'. Expected number of downloads can vary significantly according to discipline, field and language. Downloads may be split across more than one platform if the item has been deposited more than once. Not all platforms record views and downloads to the same standards, so metrics may not be comparable unless using the COUNTER standard.
Supporting	Altmetric attention insight	The reach and/or visibility of an output but not the nature of the attention it received (+ve/-ve), or its impact.	This only captures attention from sources online tracked by Altmetrics. Attention could be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'. Expected attention can vary significantly according to discipline, field and language. Consider that a raw altmetric score tells little and the nature of the attention and the context is required to communicate the impact.

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Supporting	Whether the output is open access	The visibility and accessibility of the output but not the reach or impact.	Consider whether the output is: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - discoverable and accessible without embargo or conditions - suitably documented (if data, code etc.) to support reuse - under a license that supports reuse .
Supporting	Whether the output shows evidence of open research practices.	The visibility and accessibility of the associated data of the output but not the reach or impact. Whether the output and data have been made 'FAIR' (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reproducible).	Consider whether there is evidence of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pre-registration - publication of methods, protocols, etc. - co-design or participatory research methods - deposit of supporting software, code etc - further open research as a result of the output It may be more or less appropriate or achievable to make research data FAIR according to the discipline, fields or methodology.

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Supporting	Journal identity	The identity of the publisher, but not the reach and/or visibility of the specific output, the quality of the output, or its impact.	The University does not support using journal identity as an automatic indicator of quality. It can be an indicator of the most appropriate venue to reach the intended audience for a particular output. There are many reasons why a research output would be published in a journal outside of those 'top-ranked' within a discipline (e.g. interdisciplinarity). The quality and content of the output is more important than the publication venue. However, the University does encourage publication in non-predatory journals with robust peer review processes.
Supporting	Book publisher	The identity of the publisher, but not the reach and/or visibility of the specific output, the quality of the output, or its impact.	The size and prominence of the most appropriate publisher will vary significantly according to discipline, field, and language. The quality and content of the output is more important than the publication venue.

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